

The number of even integers greater than 2 that satisfy Goldbach's conjecture

Kyumin Nam

February 2, 2022

Every even integer greater than 2 can be written as the sum of two primes.^[1]

-Leonhard Euler-

Abstract

There are infinitely many even integers greater than 2 that satisfy Goldbach's conjecture.

Contents

1. Introduction	2
2. The form of prime number	2
3. The number of even integers greater than 2 that satisfy Goldbach's conjecture	3
4. Conclusion	4
5. Reference	4

Introduction

In this paper, we provide the number of even integers greater than 2 that satisfy Goldbach's conjecture. This result will be some help for solving Goldbach's conjecture.

The form of prime number^[2]

Let's say that prime number p is satisfy:

$$p \equiv r \pmod{6}$$

Here, there are 6 possible r :

$$r = 0 \text{ or } r = 1 \text{ or } r = 2 \text{ or } r = 3 \text{ or } r = 4 \text{ or } r = 5$$

(i) $r = 0$

If $r = 0$, then since $p \equiv 0 \pmod{6}$ so p will be able to divide by 6. In other words, if $r = 0$, then $6 \mid p$. Here, since we know that p is prime number so r cannot be 0.

$$\therefore r \neq 0$$

(ii) $r = 1$

If $r = 1$, then since $p \equiv 1 \pmod{6}$ so p can be prime number. This is because by the definition of congruence, it is $p \equiv 1 \pmod{6}$. $\iff 6 \mid p-1$. Here, 6 can divide $p-1$, even p is prime number. So, r can be 1.

$$\therefore r = 1$$

(iii) $r = 2$

If $r = 2$, then since $p \equiv 2 \pmod{6}$ so p will be able to divide by 2. This is because by the definition of congruence, it is $p \equiv 2 \pmod{6}$. $\iff 6 \mid p-2 \implies 2 \mid p-2$. Here, since $2 \mid 2$ so it must be $2 \mid p$. However, a contradiction arises in the assumption that p is prime number. In other words, r cannot be 2.

$$\therefore r \neq 2$$

(iv) $r = 3$

If $r = 3$, then since $p \equiv 3 \pmod{6}$ so p will be able to divide by 3. This is because by the definition of congruence, it is $p \equiv 3 \pmod{6}$. $\iff 6 \mid p-3 \implies 3 \mid p-3$. Here, since $3 \mid 3$ so it must be $3 \mid p$. However, a contradiction arises in the assumption that p is prime number. In other words, r cannot be 3.

$$\therefore r \neq 3$$

(v) $r = 4$

If $r = 4$, then since $p \equiv 4 \pmod{6}$ so p will be able to divide by 2. This is because by the definition of congruence, it is $p \equiv 4 \pmod{6}$. $\iff 6 \mid p - 4 \implies 2 \mid p - 4$. Here, since $2 \mid 4$ so it must be $2 \mid p$. However, a contradiction arises in the assumption that p is prime number. In other words, r cannot be 4.

$$\therefore r \neq 4$$

(vi) $r = 5$

If $r = 5$, then since $p \equiv 5 \pmod{6}$ so p can be prime number. This is because by the definition of congruence, it is $p \equiv 5 \pmod{6}$. $\iff 6 \mid p - 5$. Here, 6 can divide $p - 5$, even p is prime number. So, r can be 5.

$$\therefore r = 5$$

By the (i), (ii), (iii), (iv), (v), and (vi), it is

$$p \equiv 1 \pmod{6} \text{ or } p \equiv 5 \pmod{6}$$

But, since $5 \equiv -1 \pmod{6}$ so

$$p \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{6}$$

Here, by the definition of congruence, it is

$$6 \mid p \mp 1$$

Therefore, the prime number p has the form of:

$$p = 6k \pm 1 \quad (k \in \mathbb{N})$$

The number of even integers greater than 2 that satisfy Goldbach's conjecture

Let's say that two prime number p_1 , and p_2 is equal to

$$p_1 = 6k_1 \pm 1, p_2 = 6k_2 \pm 1 \quad (k_1, k_2 \in \mathbb{N})$$

And, let's say that the even integer greater then 2 as

$$2n \quad (n > 1, n \in \mathbb{N})$$

By the Goldbach's conjecture, it is

$$2n = p_1 + p_2$$

Since $p_1 + p_2 = 6(k_1 + k_2) \pm 2$ so it is

$$n = 3(k_1 + k_2) \pm 1$$

Here, since there are infinitely many prime numbers there are infinitely many k_1 and k_2 that make p_1 and p_2 as prime numbers.

Thus, there are infinitely many n .

Therefore, **There are infinitely many even integers greater than 2 that satisfy Goldbach's conjecture.**

Conclusion

In this paper, we provided the form of prime number, and the number of even integers greater than 2 that satisfy Goldbach's conjecture. We found that the prime number p has the form of $p = 6k \pm 1$ ($k \in \mathbb{N}$). Finally, we were able to conclude that **There are infinitely many even integers greater than 2 that satisfy Goldbach's conjecture** using the above form of prime number.

Reference

- [1] ["Goldbach's conjecture"](#). wikipedia.com. Last edited on 26 January 2022.
- [2] ["Primality test"](#). wikipedia.com. Last edited on 28 January 2022.